

HUMAN RIGHTS

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The law is written and unwritten. Lack of rights - too. (Yu Bester)

Annotation: This article examines the history of human rights, a declaration known to all as the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights”. The purpose of this article is to provide precise information about these rights.

Key concepts: UN-United Nations, Human rights, Natural laws-Natural rights.

Vulnerable segments of the population: Pensioners, disabled people, etc.

Human rights are rights that we each own. The earth is home to 7.753 billion people and each of them has human rights. These rights are inalienable rights of each of us regardless of nation, citizenship, skin color, religion, language, etc.

Everyone has the right to freely participate in the cultural life of society, enjoy art, participate in scientific progress and enjoy its benefits.

Article 1 of the International Declaration of Human Rights So why did human rights arise?

They arose because a person, in addition to physical, also has a moral and spiritual essence. Human rights are needed to protect and preserve the humanity of everyone, to ensure that everyone has a decent life - the life that a person deserves. Human rights are necessary for humanity to maintain balance in the world Everything. Criminals, heads of state, children, men, women, Africans, Americans, Europeans, refugees, stateless persons, unemployed workers, bankers, terrorist indictments, charity workers, teachers, ballet dancers, astronauts ... Everyone has human rights.

Even today, there is no country in the world where all human rights are fully observed. In some countries, violations may occur more often than in others, affecting a larger or smaller part of the population, but even a single violation is a problem that should not arise and should be addressed. A person whose rights have been violated in a country with an established democracy is unlikely to find it easier because, on the whole, the situation in his country with respect to human rights is better than in other countries of the world.

History of human rights:

In 539 BC. the army of Cyrus the Great, the first king of ancient Persia, conquered the city of Babylon.

But his following actions were a huge achievement for humanity. He freed the slaves, declared that all people have the right to choose their own religion, and declared racial equality.

These and his other decrees were written in cuneiform on a cylinder of baked clay. From Babylon, the idea of human rights quickly spread to India, Greece and eventually Rome.

There the idea of "natural law" was born, since it was noticed that people tend to follow certain unwritten rules in life, and Roman law was based on rational ideas, Great development - even if sometimes it seems like a drop in the ocean. Let's think about ending slavery, giving women the right to vote, countries that have abolished the death penalty, freeing prisoners of conscience as a result of international pressure, the collapse of the South African regime, the cases brought before the European Court of Justice and the laws amended as a result. ... We need to think about the fact that the gradual development of a culture of international communication means that even the most authoritarian regimes today have to not forget about human rights if they want to be accepted by international law. There have been many positive results, especially over the past fifty years, but much more remains to be done in the future.

The moment of disappearance of human rights has approached the 20th century. The reason for this was two global world wars, human rights were in the balance of death. Many concentration camps were created, numerous murders, deaths of children. Defenseless disabled people, pensioners, women, etc.

Hunger what caused cannibalism:

Historians continue to debunk common myths about the blockade of Leningrad. Cannibalism is one of the most delicate and terrible blockade topics. For many decades, both serious researchers and social media users have been arguing whether this could have happened in Leningrad, and if so, in what quantities. Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor of the European University Nikita Lomagin brought the official statistics of the NKVD in the studio of the City +. “Of course, the hunger was the most severe, there can be no doubt about that. And terrible things happened, too. But the materials of the NKVD administration at our disposal allow us to name some figures more precisely. In fact, even in the fierce winter of 1941-1942, people who committed such crimes were negligible - 0.1% of the multimillion city” says the historian.

The collapse of states after 1945, it was necessary for someone to keep the balance in the future in the world. And so the "United Nations Organization" was created.

In 1945, following the end of World War II, the most destructive of all wars in human history, representatives from 50 countries gathered in San Francisco for the United Nations Conference on the Establishment of an International Organization to Develop a UN Charter.

After the creation of the UN, a law was needed that would further guarantee the rights of all people on the planet, a law that would guarantee people equality, freedom of speech, etc. The creation of the Declaration of Human Rights was a merit of state activities. Eleanor Roosevelt to the wife of the 26th President of the United States.

We can conclude: over 100 years after continuous wars, humanity has made tremendous progress. BUT, despite the tremendous progress, more than a hundred people die of hunger every day? Why is there still a slave trade in some countries? Why in some regions people do not have the right to freedom of speech? There is the death penalty, girls are not given out of their own free will! We must prove that the Declaration of Human Rights is not just words on paper! We must fight violence, be humane (just not lose humanity).

ЛИТЕРАТУРА:

1. Абашидзе А. Х. Договорные органы по правам человека : учебное пособие/ А. Х. Абашидзе; Рос. ун-т дружбы народов. -Москва: РУДН, 2012.-390 с.; Библиогр. в конце гл. -ISBN 978-5-209-04331-7. Имеются экземпляры в отделах: БЮФ(5)
2. Абашидзе А. Х. Международная защита экономических, социальных и культурных прав человека : программа курса/ А. Х. Абашидзе, А. Е. Конева, А. М. Солнцев. -Москва: Российский университет дружбы народов, 2015.-165, [1] с.; -Библиогр.: